

Structures of Fatty Acids from the Oil of *Argemone mexicana**

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Two fatty acids have been isolated from the oil of *Argemone mexicana* seeds. From the study of mass spectral fragmentation pattern, IR and NMR spectra coupled with various chemical reactions these two acids have been characterised as 11-oxo-triacontanoic acid (Ia) and 11-hydroxy triacontanoic acid (Ib). The properties of the former appear to be identical with those of the recently reported uncharacterised compound designated as sanguinarine potentiating factor (SPF) isolated from the oil and the latter is a new acid isolated for the first time from a natural source.

THE toxicity of argemone oil is well known and its admixture with mustard oil which is widely used in north eastern India as an edible oil causes epidemic dropsy. The toxicity is attributed to the presence in the oil of the alkaloid sanguinarine. Recently Rukmini reported¹ that the oil obtained by screw-pressing was highly toxic while the solvent extracted oil was without toxicity, though it contained amounts of sanguinarine equal to those in screw-pressed oil. It was further pointed out that a solid fatty acid derivative which was presented in screw-pressed oil but absent in solvent extracted oil might be necessary to potentiate the toxic effects of sanguinarine. The identity of this compound, however, has not been established, but it was mentioned that the product isolated could not be reduced with NaBH₄ and a 2 : 4 DNP could not be obtained indicating absence of a free :CO group. It was thought that it is likely to be an internal lactone of a derivative of ricinoleic acid with a C₈ acid. This has recently been investigated by us.

With a view to establish the chemical constitution of the compound we followed the same isolation procedure and could isolate a mixture of two compounds : Compound A (about 90%) and Compound B (about 10%) from the oil. On elemental analysis Compound A was found to have molecular formula, C₃₀H₅₈O₃ (466, M⁺), m.p. 102°-3°. The IR spectrum showed peaks at 1705 (carbonyl), 3010 (broad, bonded hydroxyl) and 719, 728 cm⁻¹ (doublet, methylene chain). The NMR spectrum showed a multiplet centred at δ 2.65 corresponding to 6H indicating the presence of three methylene groups adjacent to carbonyl groups, and a broad singlet at 1.51 ascribable to H of (CH₂)_n indicating the presence of a

methylene chain. The presence of a ketonic function was ascertained by NaBH₄ reduction of compound A when a hydroxy compound, molecular formula, C₃₀H₆₀O₃, m.p. 108°-10° was obtained. On the other hand, Compound A on treatment with ethereal solution of CH₂N₂ furnished a mono methyl ester, molecular formula, C₃₁H₆₀O₃, m.p. 78°, IR 1730 (ester carbonyl), NMR δ 3.90 (3H, s, -C-OCH₃)

suggesting the presence of a carboxyl group.

The foregoing evidences showed that Compound A was a keto acid. That it was a straight chain keto acid of the normal series was definitely proved when it could be converted to *n*-triacontanoic acid², C₃₀H₆₀O₂, m.p. 93°-94° on Huang-Minlon reduction³.

The position of the ketonic function at C-11 was evident from the mass spectral fragmentation pattern⁴ of the acid (Scheme 1). The molecular ion peak appeared at m/e 466 (M⁺, 3%). The other significant peaks appeared at m/e 452 (M⁺ - CH₂, 9), 438 (M⁺ - 2CH₂, 10), 424 (M⁺ - 3CH₂, 11), 310 (fragment a, 53), 295 (a - CH₃, 27), 282 (a - 2CH₂, 92), 267 (a - CH₃(CH₂)₂ or a - C(OH)(CH₂, 45), 252 (d, 10), 214 (c, 100), 197 (c - OH, 37), 196 (c - H₂O, 81), 156 (b, 24), 139 (b - OH, 25), 138 (b - H₂O, 46), 111 (b - COOH, 48), 96 (b - CH₂COOH, 56). Consequently, the Compound A was identified as 11-ketotriacontanoic acid⁵. The IR and NMR data and the m.p. of the acid are quite in agreement with those of Sanguinarine potentiating factor (*loc. cit.*).

Compound B (Ib) was found to have molecular formula, C₃₀H₆₀O₃, (468, M⁺), m.p. 110°, IR 3310 (hydroxyl), 1705 (acid carbonyl), 718, 728 cm⁻¹ (methylene chain). On treatment with ethereal

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Scheme - I

solution of CH_2N_2 it furnished a mono methyl ester, $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{62}\text{O}_3$, mp. $82^\circ\text{--}84^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D + 4.9^\circ$, IR 1735 (ester carbonyl), NMR δ 3.91 ($-\text{COCH}_3$). The methyl

ester on acetylation with Ac_2O and pyridine afforded an acetate, $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{64}\text{O}_4$, (540 M^+), m.p. $62^\circ\text{--}63^\circ$, NMR δ 2.01 ($-\text{COCH}_3$). It was evident therefore, that the

Compound B was a straight chain hydroxy acid. The mass spectral fragmentation pattern (Scheme II) of the acid indicated the presence of hydroxyl group at C-11. Besides the molecular ion peak at 468 (M^+ , 4), the other significant peaks discernible were at m/e 454 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{CH}_2$, 25), 297 (fragment c, 5), 267 (a, 10), 201 (b, 50), 184 (b -OH, 25), 183 (b - H_2O , 100), 171 (d, 5) and 156 (b -COOH, 25). It follows therefore that NaBH_4 reduction product of Compound A should be identical with Compound B. In fact these were found to be identical in all respects (m.p., Co-TLC and IR). Moreover, Compound B could be converted to Compound A by oxidation with Jones reagent.

Scheme - II

1a R = O

1b. R = H, OH

The occurrence of a second redox system in argemone oil—the 11-oxo- and 11-hydroxy—triacontanoic acids is of interest in relation to the sanguinarine—dihydro sanguinarine system. The proportion of sanguinarine to dihydro sanguinarine in argemone seeds has been reported to vary depending on the conditions and duration of storage⁶. It would be of interest to examine if there is any interaction between these redox systems with an equilibrium being established between the levels of the oxidized and reduced components of the systems. Secondly, evidence has recently been presented⁷ that the reaction between sanguinarine and the reduced form of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NADH_2) and consequent increase in the NAD/NADH_2 ratio in sub-cellular tissue compartments may be involved in the biochemical lesion produced by the ingestion of sanguinarine. The effect of the keto- and hydroxy-acids system identified in the present work on the reaction between sanguinarine and NADH_2 is thus of interest in connection with the potentiating action that the system has been reported to have on sanguinarine toxicity. Work on these aspects is in progress.

Experimental

M.p.s were determined in open capillary tubes in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were taken in nujol mulls and rotations in CHCl_3 solutions unless stated otherwise. NMR spectra were recorded at 60 MHz in CDCl_3 with TMS as internal reference and mass spectra were determined at an ionizing potential of 70 eV. Petroleum ether used had b.p. $60^\circ\text{--}80^\circ$ and TLC was performed on silica gel G (E. Merck).

Isolation of 11-keto triacontanoic acid (1a) and 11-hydroxy triacontanoic acid (1b):

The seeds of *Argemone mexicana* (500 g) were powdered and then extracted with petroleum ether in a soxhlet for 30 hr. The solvent was removed and the oil obtained was kept in a refrigerator overnight. Crystals appeared, the oil was allowed to come to room temperature and then filtered under

suction. The residue was washed repeatedly with petroleum to remove any contaminated oil (yield 800 mg). On TLC examination it was found to be a mixture of two compounds (one major and the other minor). Effective separation was achieved through the preparation of their methyl esters with ethereal solution of CH_2N_2 in the usual way followed by column chromatography over acid washed alumina. Methyl ester of (Ia) (yield 530 mg) was crystallised from methanol as needles, m.p. $77^\circ\text{--}78^\circ$, IR 1730 (ester carbonyl), 1705 (ketone), 717 and 728 cm^{-1} (methylene chain). Found : C, 77.55; H, 12.49; calc. for $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{60}\text{O}_3$: C, 77.44; H, 12.58%.

Methyl ester of (Ib) (yield 55 mg) was also crystallised from methanol in needles, m.p. $82^\circ\text{--}84^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D +4.9^\circ$, IR 3310 (hydroxyl), 1735 (ester carbonyl), 717 and 729 cm^{-1} (methylene chain). Found : C, 77.09; H, 13.02; $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{62}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 77.11; H, 12.94%.

On refluxing methyl ester of (Ia) with 10% ethanolic KOH for 3 hr and working up in the usual way the keto acid (Ia) was obtained which crystallised from MeOH- CHCl_3 mixture as flakes, m.p. $102^\circ\text{--}103^\circ$, IR 3010 (broad, bonded hydroxyl), 1705 (acid carbonyl), 719 and 728 cm^{-1} (methylene chain). Found : C, 77.20; H, 12.39; calc. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{58}\text{O}_3$: C, 77.19; H, 12.53%.

11-Hydroxy acid (Ib) was similarly obtained from its methyl ester and crystallised from MeOH- CHCl_3 mixture as flakes, m.p. 110° , IR 3310 (hydroxyl), 1705 (acid carbonyl), 718 and 728 cm^{-1} (methylene chain). Found : C, 76.75; H, 13.01; $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{60}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 76.86; H, 12.90%.

Conversion of (Ia) to (Ib) by NaBH_4 reduction :

To a solution of (Ia) (100 mg) in methanol (50 ml) NaBH_4 (200 mg) was added. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 3 hr with a magnetic stirrer when the whole of the ketone was converted into alcohol (TLC). Working up in the usual way the product obtained had m.p. 110° identical with (Ib) in all respects (m.p., Co-TLC and IR).

Huang-Minlon reduction of (Ia) to form n-triacontanoic acid :

300 mg of (Ia), 500 mg of KOH, 15 ml of diethylene glycol and 2 ml of 85% hydrazine hydrate were refluxed for one and half hr. Then the water was drained from the condenser and the temperature was allowed to rise to 195° . Refluxing was continued for 5 hr more. The reaction mixture was cooled,

diluted with water and poured slowly into 6N HCl. Working up in the usual way the product obtained was crystallised from methanol to yield n-triacontanoic acid, m.p. $93^\circ\text{--}94^\circ$. Found : C, 79.49; H, 13.48; calc. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{60}\text{O}_2$: C, 79.57; H, 13.36%.

Acetylation of the methyl ester of (Ib) :

Methyl ester of (Ib) (40 mg) on acetylation with acetic anhydride (3 ml) and pyridine (0.5 ml) at water bath temperature yielded the acetate, m.p. $62^\circ\text{--}63^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D +9.8^\circ$, IR 1735, 1730, 1240 (ester and acetate carbonyls), 718 and 728 cm^{-1} (methylene chain). Found : C, 75.69; H, 12.14; $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{64}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 75.51; H, 12.29%.

Conversion of (Ib) to (Ia) :

To a solution of 50 mg of (Ib) in acetone (20 ml) was added Jones reagent (prepared by dissolving 10 g of CrO_3 in 10 ml of conc. H_2SO_4 and making it 45 ml with water) drop by drop while shaking until a permanent orange colour persisted. The shaking was continued for 3 hr and left overnight. Working up in the usual way the keto acid obtained was found to be identical with 11-keto triacontanoic acid (Ia) in all respects (m.p., Co-TLC, IR).

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